

PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMED CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CHOLELITHIASIS OF THE GERONTOLOGICAL GROUP OF THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Relevance. According to the WHO, in the modern treatment and diagnostic process of cholelithiasis (CSD) it is important, especially in individuals of the gerontological group (75-90 years and above), not only to provide scientific information on a certain type of treatment (surgical or conservative) and clinical and fundamental recommendations, but also to acquire modern innovative technologies acceptable for preventive surgery and the ability to use them. For the advanced development of CSD surgery in the 21st century, it is important to identify the most susceptible individuals with high or very high risk for this pathology and their special prevention to ensure the process of early detection, effective and safe treatment (with proper pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiological screening) and the prevention of not only CSD itself, but also formidable complications of cholecystectomy, cholecystostomy, choledochotomy, choledochomyotomy and transduodenal sphincteropylotomy.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, pharmacoepidemiology of cholelithiasis and its main risk factors among the male and female unorganized population of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley to enable scientifically based planning and optimization of early diagnosis, prevention and treatment of this disease.

The object of the study was a contingent of 4,500 individuals of the gerontological age population, formed using random number tables based on the nominal electoral lists of men and women in three regions of the Fergana Valley; as well as 779 patients with cholelithiasis who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the regional multidisciplinary hospitals of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana (for VEN analysis).

The subject of the study: were the results of general clinical and biochemical blood tests, survey, physical, instrumental and

pharmacoepidemiological monitoring; as well as the method of "daily nutrition reproduction" adapted to the peculiarities of Uzbek cuisine.

Research methods. To solve the set tasks, epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, pharmacoepidemiological and statistical research methods were used, as well as the "daily nutrition reproduction" method.

Results of the study: form-coepidemiological analysis of the performed conservative treatment in patients with cholelithiasis of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley.

The analysis showed that conservative treatment was performed in 86.3% of women and 13.7% of men with cholelithiasis of the gerontological age of the Fergana Valley [$\chi^2 = 463.6$; $P < 0.001$; $RR = 0.158$; $95\% \text{ CI} = 0.125-0.201$].

Conservative therapy was mainly carried out with the following groups of drugs: antihypertensives, antispasmodics, analgesics, antibacterials, enzyme inhibitors, infusion agents, NSAIDs, anticoagulants and proton inhibitors. Considering the importance and preventive significance of the issue in optimizing treatment, pharmacoprophylaxis and pharmacovigilance of cholelithiasis in individuals of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley as a whole, the main principle is observed: "conservative/drug therapy" is indicated for gerontological patients with cholelithiasis as preoperative preparation. It is taken into account that drug therapy is indicated for gerontological patients only in cases where there are no destructive changes in the wall of the gallbladder, technical jaundice with a high anesthetic risk, when the patient refuses surgical intervention. Based on medical records/case histories, the presence of criteria for diagnosing catarrhal and destructive cholecystitis against the background of cholelithiasis in each geriatric patient was assessed (S. F. Bagzhenko, 2015):

In addition, for comparison during the analysis, the following was adopted as the basic (generally accepted, corresponding to the latest clinical recommendations) therapy: probing and aspiration of gastric contents, the use of drugs such as antispasmodic solutions, antibacterial drugs, analgesics, infusion therapy (in a volume of 40 ml per 1 kg of body weight) with crystalloid solutions and oral litholytic therapy

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